

Emotional Contagion And Its Relationship With Daily Hassles Among The Educational Counselors

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Article Info	Abstract
Article History Received: July 02, 2020 Accepted: August 29, 2020	<i>The aim of the research was to identify the emotional contagion and its relation to the daily agitation of educational counselors. The researcher used the descriptive method and the sample of the study reached (100) educational counselors. The researcher used two Scales: the Emotional contagion scale and the daily Hassles scale. The validity of both instruments was verified (face, and construction) and consistency of the instruments using the re-test, and internal consistency Cronbach's alpha. Emotional contagion among Educational Counselors was (49.2500) this refers to a higher level, compared with the theoretical average of (45). Daily Hassles among Educational Counselors was (164.0500) this refers to a higher level, compared with the theoretical average of (150) .The research found that there is a significant correlation between the emotional contagion and daily Hassles of the female counselors.</i>
Keywords Emotional Contagion, Daily Hassles, And Educational Counselors	
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1. Introduction

The educational counselor deals with the female instructors in all aspects of their emotional, social and educational personalities. This requires from her a great deal of awareness and understanding of the positions of the female counselors and looking at them from the same angle of the counselor, sympathizing with her, and feeling her emotions through interaction with her as a result of emotional contagion.

Emotional contagion is an important element of empathy. Hatfield and others (Hatfield et al, 2010) emphasized the importance of the individual's ability to exchange feelings with another and to have the ability to feel the feelings of the other individual (Hatfield et al, 2010, p. 42) .The extension process requires the educational counselor to interact with the counselor in realizing her feelings and responding to them, and in return, the educational counselor is exposed to the various and different Daily Hassles due to the difficult conditions that the society is going through, including social, economic, political and cultural challenges. It is burdened by the growing daily Hassles and its repetition and accumulation, such as family conditions and the lack of necessary services in daily life, as well as road surprises, which are environmental events and situations that bother individuals in general, and the educational counselor in particular.

The educational counselors have an important and influential position, as they represent an effective segment in society. Therefore, it is necessary for the educational counselor to be able to confront Daily Hassles that cause the various problems, difficulties and pressures that she is exposed to in her daily life, and the problem of the current research stems from a fact that the researcher perceives through her experience of reality, and Her field experience. It became clear to her that many of the female educational counselors need to communicate and feel the feelings of the female guides and realize their emotions, and to be able to confront Daily Hassles. Therefore, the current research problem addresses the identification of Emotional contagion and its relationship with the Daily Hassles among the educational counselors, because no study was conducted - according to the researcher's knowledge - These two variables were examined by the educational counselors.

Research importance:

The importance of psychological counseling in the school is evident through the role played by the educational counselor, who has been prepared in an academic, theoretical and practical manner. She was provided with scientific information and professional, academic and applied skills in universities, and she was trained in psychological counseling centers and psychiatric clinics in schools under the supervision of specialists (Schuman, 2008: p. 8).

The educational counselor has an important role in the counseling process in guiding female counselors, which requires them to explore and understand the problems facing them and help them to solve them objectively and confront the resulting conflict. And commitment to the self and mental guidance of the female guides, caring for them, solving their problems, and participating with them in the completion of some of the tasks that they perform, as well as a sense of their needs and feelings (Gilligan, 1982: 37). The social environment, its self-assessment, capabilities and realistic potential can choose the best available alternatives.

And the counseling process takes place in a calm psychological atmosphere and in appropriate natural conditions between the counselor and the counselor who came to seek help to solve her problems (Al-Khatib, 2004: p. 190), so the educational counselor realizes the events, situations, and problems facing the female counselors and reduces their impact through interaction with them, and awareness of their feelings that occurs through Emotional contagion, which enables the educational counselor to interact with the counselor.

Emotional contagion is an influencing factor in social relations, as it enhances the simultaneous emotion between individuals in the social situation, so there is a process of conscious or unconscious interaction for a group of emotions and behavioral situations by the individual or group of individuals by influencing the emotions or behavior of an individual or group of individuals (Schoenewolf, 1990, p 50).

Daily life is full of troubles and troubles that face individuals, whether within the family or in the field of work, and it affects the health of the educational counselor and her mood in the long term, and her abilities to perform her work, as Daily Hassles prevents the educational counselor from achieving important goals, so she considers unnecessary. Daily Hassles can turn into a major source of stress when they build up and recur. Greenberg, 2014, p.net)), and the success of the work is based on the educational counselor's possession of a set of specifications that make her able to help others, and integrate her academic knowledge with her personal characteristics, skills and abilities to help in the counseling process, and dealing with Daily Hassles shows through her ability Her adaptation to various counseling situations, her skills in communicating with others, her adaptation and her ability to deal with Daily Hassles has a positive impact on providing counseling services that respond to the counselors' situations and needs (Spring et al, 1995, p. 1015). The researcher believes that the educational counselor's awareness of the Emotional contagion and her ability to confront Daily Hassles enables her to take effective and active positions in the counseling process and meet the needs of the female counselors. The problem of the current research stems from the fact that the researcher perceives through her experience of the reality that the effects of the reality of life and the circumstances that led to the occurrence of many changes in the life of Iraqi society.

Research aims:

The current research aims to identify:

- Emotional contagion at the educational counselors.
- Daily Hassles for educational counselors.
- The relationship between Emotional contagion and Daily Hassles among educational counselors.

Search limits:

The current research is limited to female educational counselors working in intermediate, preparatory and secondary schools affiliated with the Ministry of Education in all governorates of Iraq except for the Kurdistan region for the academic year (2016-2017).

Defining terms:

1- Emotional Contagion:

- Hatfield, & et al (1992) defined it as: automatic simulation synchronized with vocalizations and facial expressions, movements and positions with the other person, and thus, emotionally close with the other person.

Epstude&Mussweiler, (2009): defined it as a conscious process of comparing emotional states between people that occurs through social situations, evaluating these cases with others and evoking appropriate reactions.

- The researcher adopted the definition of Hatfield, & et al (1992), a theoretical definition of emotional contagion for the research.

- The Emotional Contagion Researcher procedurally defines it as the total score obtained by the educational counselor through her response to the statements of the Emotional Contagion Scale prepared by Doherty (1997) as a tool for this research.

2- Daily Hassles :

Kanner, et al., (1981) defined it as everyday troubles that occur daily and are repeated in a manner that annoying and frustrating demands to some extent characterizes daily dealings with the environment.

Malia et al. (1979) defined it as Daily Hassles that occurs frequently and frequently in personal relationships or routine aspects of life that have an impact on an individual's life or family life.

- The researcher adopted the definition of Kanner, et al., (1981), a theoretical definition of the daily nuisances of the research.

- The researcher defined Daily Hassles, procedurally as the total score obtained by the educational counselor for the research sample through her response to the items of the Daily Hassles scale prepared by the researcher and used in this research.

Theoretical framework:

First: Emotional contagion:

Emotional contagion is a multi-level phenomenon that results from stimuli that occur to a single individual, or group of individuals, to act (i.e. understand and interpret) and result in similar or complementary feelings (knowledge, awareness, facial expression, autonomic nervous system functioning, and overall

emotional behavior of responses) in these individuals. . Emotional contagion is attention, emotion and simultaneous behavior to help adjust to the opposite individual or social group.

(Hatfield et al., 1992, p. 153-154)

Facial imitation is an important aspect of Emotional contagion because it is the aspect that can be observed completely by others, and the individual during the interaction observes the movements of the opposite person and then receives emotions through facial expressions. McIntosh, 2006, p.31) that blind imitation of the face can happen spontaneously By simply observing others indicating that individuals automatically match their behaviors and feelings with others in their social environment. And that these interactions can be attributed to emotional or cognitive processes (Hess, et al, 1998, p. 509).

Emotional contagion may be important in interpersonal relationships: as it promotes behavioral synchronization and traces feelings with others moment by moment, and even when individuals do not explicitly obtain the information, i.e., subconsciously follow in simulating others (Hatfield et al., 1992, p. 6)

Emotional contagion does not occur only in real human interaction, but rather is found in human communication through technological communication and other means of communication. Hancock, et al. (2008) conducted a study to observe the expression of emotions in computer communications, and if the recipient individual could sense emotions, and that Emotional contagion could occur in communications at the level of text exchange as well.

Emotional contagion cases:

Three cases were identified in which emotional contagion occurs, namely:

1- During dialogue and conversations: individuals automatically and continuously imitate others, and facial expressions, voices, attitudes, movements, behaviors and actions coincide with other individuals.

2- The effect of a subjective emotional experience: the simultaneous imitation occurs as a kind of reaction moment after moment as a result of an emotional experience experienced by the individual.

3- The tendency of the individual to imitate others, imitate them, and imitate their emotions, moment by moment. (Hatfield & Rapson, 2010, p.1-2)

Emotional contagion factors:

Multiple factors can contribute to emotional contagion events. Coenen and Broekens (2012) classify factors into three groups:

1- Internal factors: Evidence showed that the occurrence of Emotional contagion is stronger within groups than outside groups.

2- Individual differences: Individual differences have an important and influential role in Emotional contagion. There are individuals who pay great attention to the feelings of others, and on the contrary there are individuals whose communication with others is weak.

3- Other factors:

Mood: Weak evidence revealed that an individual's mood influences the emergence of emotional contagion, so when he is happy, he is more likely to have it.

Gender: Sex plays a large role in emotional contagion, as females in general are to some extent more susceptible to Emotional contagion than males.

Occupation: students are generally more vulnerable to emotional contagion than individuals of other professions, and the reason is that students have not chosen a profession yet, which makes them more vulnerable to emotional contagion (Coenen&Broekens, 2012, p. 56)

Second: daily problems

Everyday problems are a day-to-day problem that has led to the individual, anger and frustration. It is characterized by daily interactions with others and the environment surrounding him, which causes a problem in topics or objective bottlenecks or an error in setting personal items, or the pressures of the period facing ordinary individuals of daily life (Kanner, et al., 1981, p. 35). McIntyre et al. (McIntyre, et al., 2008) described everyday problems that cause anger, frustration, and painful demands that occur in everyday situations everyday problems and troublesome practical troubles, and difficulties (McIntyre et al, 2008, p. 383). Financial and family disputes and remnants, which are in the name of daily troubles, and the relationship of daily life, such as traffic jams and phone calls outside of their times, and daily problems are frequent occurring troubles to the individual or family in the context of work or marriage (Kanner, et al. 1981, p. 25), the extent of individual compatibility, daily barriers are a predominant indicator of stress, and many studies have not used everyday emotions as a concept of fatigue alone or in association with life events (Garrison 1990, p.22). Also describing these daily and personal events (Hajar, 2007, p. 9).

A study conducted by (Kanner, et al, 1981) revealed that daily problems fit with psychological symptoms of life events, and daily problems have more than life events, and daily problems about them. Kanner, et al,

(1981, p. 139), and Kanron et al. (1981) see its nature as defined by these as timing, frequency and intensity, duration, and frequency.

But Rich et al. (1988) has classified the everyday problems that developed Knner et al. (1981) in two dimensions:

Number of annoyances: It is an objective measure of daily annoyances.

The severity of the disturbances: Refers to a personal measure of daily annoyances.

The number and severity of disturbances varies in aspects of daily problems and affects stress

Variouly: Reich et al. (1988, p. 240).

The picture from the environment of life in the image that appears inside the image in the image that appears inside the image and inside the image in the image that begins with the individual life of the daily routine. Finance (Ranchor&Sanderman, 2000, p. 16).

And initiation of interaction with multiple daily life situations that are harmful or threatening individual well-being (Chamberlain and Zika, 1990, p. 470). These are common and occur together continuously among many people, including: Some things to do simultaneously Problems or difficulties with Daily Hassles(Lazarus, 1989, p. 38), as a study appeared (Garrison, 1990), a message of daily problems, and the title, and the results appeared in the daily administrative behaviors family table on behavior Garrison, 1990, p. 55-

Governorate	Total
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negatives on the of the family and the and family cohesion (107).

Research procedures:

Research methodology: The researcher adopted the descriptive research methodology on the objectives of her research.

Research community: The current research community includes female educational counselors in governmental preparatory and secondary schools in the Republic of Iraq, with the exception of the governorates of the Kurdistan region for the academic year (2016-2017). The research community consisted of (2024) educational counselors distributed over the governorates of Iraq, and Table (1) illustrates this.

Table (1)

The research community is distributed according to the governorates for the educational counselors

Governorate	General total
Baghdad	793
Najaf	50
Karbala	84
Wasit	102
Babylon	106
Kirkuk	99
Salahuddin	42
Diyala	168
Nineveh	109
Anbar	50
DhiQar	112
Double	22
Maysan	25
Basra	166
Qadisiyah	96
Total	2024

The data were taken from the Educational Guidance Division in the Ministry of Education

Main Research Sample:

The main research sample consisted of (100) educational counselors who were chosen by the random stratified method according to roughly proportional to their number in the research community. Table (2) illustrates this.

Baghdad	73
Basra	15
Maysan	2
Babylon	10
Total	100

Research Instruments:

First: Emotional contagion:

The original Emotional contagion scale:

Doherty (1997) developed the Emotional Contagion Scale, which consisted of (15) items to measure Emotional Contagion, and the scale includes five sub-emotions: (happiness, love, sadness, anger and fear) and these emotions demonstrate susceptibility to negative feelings such as sadness, anger, fear and feelings, Positivity (like happiness and love).

The scale's statements are written in the manner of reportable statements, and in front of them are alternatives with a pentagonal gradient according to Likert's method:

Always = 5, often = 4, usually = 3, rarely = 2, never = 1, and the passive statements were as follows:

(Happiness = 2, 3, 11), (love = 6, 9, and 12), and (fear = 8, 13, 15)

(Anger = 5, 7, 10), (Sadness = 1, 4, and 14).

The higher the score of the respondent on the scale, the more it showed that he was more susceptible to Emotional contagion, and that the reliability of the test and retest was high as the value of (Cronbach Alpha = 0.90), so the structure of the scale was of high internal consistency, which confirms the validity of the scale construction was sufficient.

(Doherty, 1997, p. 131-154)

Emotional contagion procedures for current research:

Validate scale:

The concept of validity refers to the degree to which the scale measures what was set to measure it (Harrison, 1983, p.1). The researcher verified the indicators of validity of the validity of the translation, appearance and construction (of the scale) as follows:

- Translation veracity:

The researcher translated the Emotional Contagion Scale into Arabic and vice versa, and the procedures were as follows:

The translation of the original copy of the scale and the translated version was presented to a group of specialists in the English language and psychological sciences to clarify their views on the proposed translation with an indication of its accuracy, and to make the appropriate amendments to the translated statements, and after taking the experts' opinions regarding the validity of the translated statements. And to offer the scale translated into Arabic to another expert in the English language to re-translate it into the English language again, to ensure the veracity of the translation for the statements of the scale, as the percentage of agreement in both cases reached (88%), which is valid according to Bloom's opinion. If the agreement among experts is 75% or more, the validity of the scale can be trusted (Bloom, 1983: p.126).

-Virtual validity:

The researcher verified the apparent validity of the scale and the appropriateness of the statements and instructions of the Emotional contagion Scale, and presented it in a questionnaire to (12) arbitrators from specialists in psychological sciences. The researcher approved the approval of (10) arbitrators or more as a criterion for the relevance of the scale statements to the sample of the current research, and no statement was excluded from the scale, so the scale consisted of (15) items.

- Construction validity:

The Construction validity, which is sometimes called the sincerity of the concept and the sincerity of the hypothetical formation, by which we mean the extent to which the psychological scale is measured to form a hypothesis or a specific psychological concept (Rabi`, 1994: p. 98). The indicators of construct validity in psychological measures appear through the ability of the statements to distinguish between The answers of the two groups are extreme on each statement in the scale, and its correlation with the total score of the scale (Anastasi, 1997, p.155), and verifying the strength of discrimination. The statements are an indication of the validity of the scale construction, and the consistency of its statements, which appears through the correlation of each statement with the total score of the scale all of them were indicative, and thus it is considered an indication of the validity of the construction of the Emotional Contagion Scale.

- Statistical analysis :

The aim of calculating the psychometric properties of the statements is to choose the appropriate ones, and to amend or exclude the inappropriate statements (Ghisell, et al, 1981: 421). Therefore, the researcher decided to calculate these indicators as follows:

Distinguishing Power of Statements:

The calculation of the discriminatory strength of the statements in the psychological measures aims to exclude the statements with weak discrimination between individuals, and to maintain the statements that distinguish between them in responses, because it reveals the strength of the scale to show individual differences between the subjects (Ebel, 1972, p. 399). The researcher measured the scale on a sample taken from the research community consisting of (200) educational counselors, and a percentage (27%) of the sample members was adopted in determining the two extremes, in the total score, and after applying the scale to the sample, their answers were arranged in descending order from the highest total score to the lowest. Then the two extremist groups were determined in the overall score of (27%) of the educational counselors in each group, so the educational counselors in each group became (54) an educational guide, and the t-test of two independent samples was used to know the significance of the difference between the two extremist groups in the grades of each statement of the scale, so it appeared that all the scale statements are distinguished at the level of (0.05) because the calculated T value is greater than the tabular T (1.96) with a degree of freedom (106). Note Table (3). Ebel (1972) emphasized that the test items are considered good and preserve them if their discriminatory strength is more than (0.30) (Ebel, 1972: 392).

Table (3)

The discriminatory power (*) of the statements of the emotional contagion scale

The relationship of the statement score to the overall score of the scale:

Empirical honesty refers to the extent to which the formative content of the trait is related to each other (Abd al-Rahma	High Group		Low group		T - value
	Mean	S.D	Mean	S.D	
1	4.407407	0.53265	1.537037	0.503308	38.854
2	4.425926	0.53560	1.648148	0.482032	39.674
3	4.574074	0.53560	1.37037	0.487438	40.979
4	4.388889	0.52903	1.574074	0.535595	37.677
5	4.444444	0.53787	1.481481	0.540466	37.649
6	4.444444	0.53787	1.518519	0.504349	38.933
7	4.407407	0.53265	1.518519	0.504349	38.816
8	4.462963	0.53950	1.518519	0.540466	37.755
9	4.481481	0.54047	1.481481	0.504349	39.176
10	4.50000	0.54079	1.481481	0.504349	39.344
11	4.555556	0.53787	1.555556	0.537874	38.813
12	4.462963	0.53950	1.407407	0.495966	39.343
13	4.611111	0.52903	1.481481	0.540466	39.663
14	4.407407	0.53265	1.518519	0.504349	38.816
15	4.518519	0.54047	1.555556	0.50157	39.646

n, 1983: p. 414) and that the statements are considered true if the correlation coefficient between them and the overall score is high. Because of the lack of an external criterion, the researcher adopted the total score of the scale as an internal criterion, as Anastasi (1997) indicated that in the absence of an external criterion, the total score of the scale is the best internal criterion (Anastasi, 1997, p. 211) according to the Pearson correlation coefficient. The score for each statement and the total score for the respondent on the Emotional contagion scale, after which the T value of the correlation coefficient for each statement was calculated. So it became clear that all the statements are statistically significant at the level of (0.05) because the T value of the calculated correlation coefficient is greater than the tabular value (1.96) with a degree of freedom (198). See Table (4)

Table (4)

The item score correlation coefficients with the overall score for the items of the Emotional Contagion scale

No	R	T- value
1	.860	23.71
2	.863	24.04

3	.873	25.19
4	.871	24.95
5	.875	25.43
6	.873	25.19
7	.857	23.40
8	.872	25.07
9	.883	26.47
10	.869	24.71
11	.878	25.81
12	.871	24.95
13	.882	26.34
14	.848	22.51
15	.876	25.56

The tabular T value at the level of significance (0.05) is (1.96), with a degree of freedom (198).

Reliability of scale:

Reliability refers to the consistency of the scores of the scale statements that are supposed to measure in what should be measured (Marshlly, 1972, p. 125). The researcher verified the consistency of the Emotional contagion scale in two ways:

1- Method of retesting:

The test is considered constant, if it gives the same results when it is repeated on the same individuals, and under the same circumstances (Al-Gharib, 1977: p.653).

The researcher applied the Emotional Contagion Scale a second time after 21 days had passed from the first application, according to what (Adams) indicated that the time period between the two applications should not exceed two or three weeks on individuals of the adult reliability sample (Adams, 1964, p. 85). Their number (50) educational counselors were chosen randomly from the sample of statistical analysis. Pearson correlation coefficient was used to calculate the reliability of the test, and it reached (0.85) and it is considered a good reliability coefficient, as (Gronlund) believes that the test is considered good, as its reliability coefficient ranged between (0.60-0.85) (Gronlund, 1981, p. 125).

2- Internal consistency using the equation of Fakrobenach:

The internal consistency of the coefficient of Fakronbach (Cronbach Alpha) is the most common type of stability, as it uses an indicator to calculate the equivalence, that is, it gives a good estimate of the parity coefficient as well as the internal consistency. If the value of the alpha coefficient is high, it actually indicates the reliability of the grades (Salah al-Din 2000: pg. 166) and the researcher adopted this method to measure the reliability of the Emotional contagion scale. It is appropriate (Al-Bayati and Zakaria 1977: p. 194).

Second: Daily Hassles Scale:

To measure Daily Hassles at educational counselors, the researcher reviewed psychological literature, previous studies, research and theoretical framework for the purpose of building a measure of daily disturbances.

It has formulated a number of statements for the Daily Hassles Scale, consisting of five fields, as the total number of statements of the scale in its initial form was (50) items.

The first field: the inconveniences of lack of time. It contains (10) statements.

The second field: social disturbances and it contains (10) statements.

The third field: financial troubles, and it contains (10) statements.

The fourth field: work inconveniences, and it contains (10) statements.

The fifth field: environmental disturbances, and it contains (10) statements.

And the answer alternatives were identified for the scale statements and their weights, since the answer alternatives for the statements are (always occurring = 5, often occurring = 4, occurring sometimes, = 3, rarely occurring = 2, never occurring = 1).

Validate scale:

For the purpose of ensuring the wording of the statements and their suitability for the five sub-fields, the statements were presented to a group of referees specialized in psychological sciences, as some simple amendments were made. (50) statements remained, and a high score on the scale indicated an increase in the daily Hassles effect, while a low score indicated a decrease in the Daily Hassles effect of educational counselors.

Exploratory experience:

- Statistical analysis of the scale statements:

Statistical analysis of statements is very important because it accurately reveals the veracity of the statements (Farag, 1980: p. 332). Psychometric experts emphasize the psychometric properties that must be present in measures statements, which are the strength of statement distinction and their validity coefficients, so the researcher decided to calculate these indicators:

Distinguishing Power of Statements:

To achieve this, he applied the Daily Hassles scale on a sample of the research community consisting of (200) educational counselors. After applying the scale to the sample members, their answers were arranged in descending order, from the highest total score to the lowest total score, then the two extremist groups were determined in the total score at (27%) of the educational counselors in each group, so the number of educational counselors in each group became 54 Educational, and after using the t-test for two independent samples to find out the significance of the difference between the upper and lower groups in the scores of each statement of the scale, all the scale statements were found distinct at the level of (0.05) because the calculated T value is greater than the tabular value (1.96) freely (106), and Table (5) shows the discriminatory strength of the scale statements.

Table (5)
Distinguishing Strength (*) Paragraphs of the daily disturbance scale

	High Group		Low group		T - value
	Mean	S.D	Mean	S.D	
1	4.296296	0.743008	1.592593	0.566969	22.764
2	4.388889	0.737581	1.666667	0.513956	23.029
3	4.50000	0.636915	1.388889	0.529031	23.109
4	4.351852	0.648872	1.611111	0.563569	24.591
5	4.333333	0.777029	1.50000	0.57462	23.705
6	4.37037	0.708341	1.537037	0.539495	25.853
7	4.333333	0.672927	1.555556	0.571878	22.940
8	4.333333	0.726844	1.555556	0.571878	22.857
9	4.444444	0.691366	1.537037	0.539495	27.612
10	4.425926	0.7673	1.518519	0.540466	22.252
11	4.462963	0.692629	1.592593	0.599324	23.668
12	4.407407	0.740181	1.462963	0.573403	25.482
13	4.407407	0.687311	1.481481	0.540466	24.597
14	4.277778	0.656367	1.537037	0.539495	22.071
15	4.37037	0.623329	1.555556	0.50157	24.363
16	4.314815	0.695649	1.648148	0.482032	23.029
17	4.388889	0.737581	1.388889	0.529031	24.542
18	4.50000	0.636915	1.611111	0.563569	22.092
19	4.333333	0.700404	1.50000	0.57462	23.226
20	4.37037	0.681184	1.518519	0.504349	23.639
21	4.388889	0.656367	1.518519	0.504349	25.668
22	4.333333	0.672927	1.555556	0.571878	22.252
23	4.333333	0.726844	1.537037	0.539495	24.267
24	4.444444	0.691366	1.537037	0.573403	24.801
25	4.462963	0.66483	1.592593	0.599324	21.544
26	4.462963	0.692629	1.425926	0.499126	25.000
27	4.407407	0.740181	1.518519	0.60628	22.857
28	4.388889	0.737581	1.518519	0.504349	24.720
29	4.259259	0.705375	1.574074	0.535595	22.770
30	4.351852	0.677326	1.574074	0.535595	23.668
31	4.351852	0.587846	1.666667	0.513956	24.101
32	4.388889	0.737581	1.37037	0.487438	23.825
33	4.444444	0.793052	1.611111	0.563569	23.887

*
The tabular T value at the level of significance (0.05) is (1.96), with a degree of freedom (198).
The relation

34	4.37037	0.592287	1.50000	0.57462	24.363
35	4.333333	0.777029	1.555556	0.50157	23.249
36	4.333333	0.644278	1.648148	0.482032	23.029
37	4.388889	0.737581	1.388889	0.529031	24.278
38	4.462963	0.745122	1.62963	0.592287	23.848
39	4.351852	0.648872	1.50000	0.57462	22.526
40	4.37037	0.681184	1.518519	0.504349	25.853
41	4.37037	0.708341	1.537037	0.539495	22.764
42	4.333333	0.672927	1.537037	0.539495	23.029
43	4.351852	0.677326	1.537037	0.539495	23.109
44	4.444444	0.691366	1.537037	0.573403	24.591
45	4.444444	0.718139	1.592593	0.599324	23.705
46	4.462963	0.692629	1.462963	0.573403	25.853
47	4.425926	0.689595	1.50000	0.57462	22.940
48	4.407407	0.687311	1.537037	0.539495	22.857
49	4.259259	0.705375	1.555556	0.50157	27.612
50	4.37037	0.623329	1.648148	0.482032	23.029

ship of the paragraph to the overall score of the scale:

The paragraph is true when the correlation coefficient between it and the total score is strong, according to the Pearson correlation coefficient between the score for each paragraph and the score on the Daily Hassles scale, and the T value of the correlation coefficient for each paragraph was calculated. The T value of the significance of the computed correlation coefficient is greater than the tabular value (1.96) with a degree of freedom (198), and Table (6) shows the validity coefficient of the paragraphs.

Table (6)
Paragraph correlation coefficients for overall score for Daily Hassles scale paragraphs

No	R	sig	No	R	sig
1	.909	30.69	26	.912	31.29
2	.907	30.31	27	.913	31.49
3	.927	34.78	28	.914	31.70
4	.911	31.08	29	.903	29.57
5	.915	31.91	30	.912	31.29
6	.911	31.08	31	.909	30.69
7	.908	30.50	32	.908	30.50
8	.910	30.88	33	.924	34.00
9	.918	32.57	34	.908	30.50
10	.916	32.13	35	.913	31.49
11	.916	32.13	36	.908	30.50
12	.912	31.29	37	.912	31.29
13	.914	31.70	38	.925	34.26
14	.906	30.12	39	.911	31.08
15	.912	31.29	40	.915	31.91
16	.913	31.49	41	.911	31.08
17	.906	30.12	42	.908	30.50
18	.929	35.32	43	.911	31.08
19	.908	30.50	44	.918	32.57
20	.916	32.13	45	.917	32.35
21	.911	31.08	46	.916	32.13
22	.915	31.91	47	.911	31.08
23	.910	30.88	48	.914	31.70

24	.919	32.80	49	.908	30.50
25	.917	32.35	50	.912	31.29

The relation of the score of the paragraph to the field: The relationship of the score of the paragraph to the field, to which the paragraph belongs, was calculated using the Pearson correlation coefficient, since the tabular value at the significance level (0.05) is (1.96). See Table (7).

Table (7)

Relation of paragraph score to field

Relation to the field	statement	field
.893	.1	The hassles of time lack
.898	.2	
.914	.3	
.895	.4	
.895	.5	
.903	.6	
.899	.7	
.896	.8	
.908	.9	
.911	.10	
.906	.11	Social hassles
.896	.12	
.903	.13	
.898	.14	
.903	.15	
.907	.16	
.890	.17	
.914	.18	
.899	.19	
.908	.20	
.904	.21	Financial hassles
.905	.22	
.899	.23	
.906	.24	
.908	.25	
.897	.26	
.903	.27	
.904	.28	
.896	.29	
.900	.30	
.906	.31	work hassles
.901	.32	
.914	.33	
.912	.34	
.911	.35	
.901	.36	
.900	.37	
.913	.38	
.910	.39	
.916	.40	
.905	.41	Environmental hassles
.899	.42	
.899	.43	
.911	.44	
.904	.45	
.905	.46	
.899	.47	

.902	.48	
.899	.49	
.902	.50	

Reliability of the scale: The reliability of the scale means that the scale is reliable, and reliance on it in giving the results that are reached in the event of applying it several times if it is applied to the same individuals, and in similar circumstances (Al-Gharib, 1985: p.653) The researcher verified the reliability of Daily Hassles scale using the internal consistency method using the Fachropanach equation and to assess the internal consistency of the Daily Hassles scale. Statistical analysis sample answers were used in the reliability calculation. The alpha coefficient reached (0.85), which is an excellent reliability coefficient for the internal consistency of the scale.

Daily Hassles scale in final form:

The scale paragraphs in its final form reached (50) paragraphs, as the answer alternatives to the paragraphs are (always happen = 5, often occurs = 4, sometimes occurs = 3, rarely occurs = 2, never happens = 1) given to her upon correction (5, 4, 3, 2, 1). The highest score for the scale is (250) and the lowest score is (50), with a hypothetical average (150).

Application of the two scales: After the two scales were prepared and their psychometric properties were verified, they were applied to the individuals of the basic research sample of (100) educational counselors. Note Table (1).

Statistical means: To achieve the objectives of the current research, the following statistical methods were used:

The T-test for two independent samples, the Pearson Correlation Coefficient, the Cronbach Alpha Coefficient, the T-test for one sample.

Displaying and interpreting results:

1- The first goal:

The first objective measures Emotional contagion at educational counselors. To achieve this, the T-test was used for one sample T-test, and the results showed that the average Emotional contagion scores for the research sample is equal to (49.2500) degrees, and with a standard deviation of (12.77100) degrees. It was in statistical significance at the level of (0.05), as the calculated T value reached (3.328), which is greater than the tabular T value (1.96) with a degree of freedom (99). Table (8) illustrates that.

Table (8)

The result of a single sample t-test for the sample scores on the Emotional Contagion scale

Sample	Hypothetical mean	Mean	S.D	Degree of freedom	T- value		sig
					calculated	tabular	
100	45	49.2500	12.77100	99	3.328	1.96	0.05

The result showed that there is a statistically significant difference between the sample mean and the hypothetical mean of the scale, which indicates that educational counselors generally have a level of Emotional contagion.

This result is consistent with the study of Doherty and others (Doherty, et al, 1995, p. 355), which revealed that women in general in different occupations have an Emotional Contagion , and they emotionally converge with the opposite person and their automatic tendency to imitate the other.

2- The second goal: The second objective was devoted to measuring the level of Daily Hassles at educational counselors. To achieve this, the T-test was used for one sample T-test, and the results showed that the average daily Hassles scores for the research sample are equal to (164.0500) degrees and a standard deviation of (47.45255) degrees. Knowing the significance of the difference between the sample mean and the hypothetical mean of the scale of (150) it became clear that the difference was in statistical significance at the level of (0.05), as the calculated T value reached (2,961), which is greater than the tabular T value (1.96) with a degree of freedom (99), see table (9).

Table (9)

The result of one sample t-test for scores on the scale of Daily Hassles

Sample	Hypothetical mean	Mean	S.D	Degree of freedom	T- value		sig
					calculated	tabular	
100	150	164.0500	47.45255	99	2.961	1.96	0.05

The result showed that there is a statistically significant difference between the sample mean and the hypothetical mean of the scale, which indicates that educational counselors generally have a level of Emotional contagion.

This result is consistent with the study of Doherty and others (Doherty, et al, 1995, p. 355), which revealed that women in general in different occupations have an Emotional Contagion , and they emotionally converge with the opposite person and their automatic tendency to imitate the other.

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Table (9)

The result of one sample t-test for the sample scores on the scale of Daily Hassles

Sample	Hypothetical mean	Mean	S.D	Degree of freedom	T- value		sig
					calculated	tabular	
100	150	164.0500	47.45255	99	2.961	1.96	0.05

This result indicates that educational counselors are generally influenced by Daily Hassles, as it affects their mood, emotions, professional competence, and their inability to confront, which leads them to a state of psychological burnout, which leads them to high levels of apathy, low motivation and loss of their ability to innovate, and their behavior in a way that lacks self-integration in their counseling works, and thus affects their relationships with others, especially for female mentors.

3- The third objective: To know the relationship between the Emotional Contagion and Daily Hassles at the educational counselors.

To achieve this goal, the researcher calculated the correlation coefficient between educational counselors' scores in Daily Hassles and Emotional Contagion, and the correlation coefficient between them reached (0.394). To verify the significance of this relationship, the T-test for the significance of the correlation coefficient was used, as shown in Table (10). The results revealed that there is a positive statistically significant relationship between Emotional contagion and Daily Hassles.

Table (10)

The correlation coefficient between Emotional Contagion and Daily Hassles at educational counselors

Variables	R	T- value	
		calculated	tabular
Emotional Contagion	0.394	4.24	1.96
Daily Hassles			

The result showed that there is a statistically significant relationship between Emotional Contagion Daily Hassles, which shows the influence of educational counselors with daily Hassles, which leads them to withdraw from interaction with social situations and their professional interaction, and they lose interest in posts with others and lead them to affect their feelings and transfer them to others because they have Emotional contagion,

which leads to They are disoriented in feeling and perceiving other people's emotions, especially for female counselors.

Conclusions: In light of the research results, the researcher concludes the following conclusions:

- The educational counselors have a level of Daily Hassles as well as a high level of Emotional contagion.

- The existence of an indicative correlation relationship between Daily Hassles and Emotional Contagion among educational counselors.

Recommendations: In light of the results that have been reached, the researcher recommends the following:

- Reducing the level of daily Hassles and protecting them from stress and psychological tension by holding periodic seminars for educational counselors and immunizing them against stress

-Motivating Emotional contagion by creating training and mentoring programs to raise their professional level.

The proposals:

-Conducting a similar study on Emotional contagion and its relationship to other variables such as cultural intelligence.

-Conducting a similar study on educational counselors according to the gender variable and comparing its results with the current research.

-Conducting a similar study on Daily Hassles and its relationship to other variables such as emotional sensitivity and others.

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